

International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies

ISSN: 2347-5129

(ICV-Poland) Impact Value: 5.62

(GIF) Impact Factor: 0.352

IJFAS 2015; 3(2): 212-217

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www.fisheriesjournal.com

Received: 18-08-2015

Accepted: 19-09-2015

BM Newaz Sharif

Department of Aquaculture,
Faculty of Fisheries, Bangladesh
Agricultural University,
Mymensingh-2202, Bangladesh.

Abdulla-Al-Asif

Department of Aquaculture,
Faculty of Fisheries, Bangladesh
Agricultural University,
Mymensingh-2202, Bangladesh.

Suvashis Vaumik

Farm Officer, Sherpur Fish
Hatchery, CP Bangladesh Co. Ltd.
Balughata, Nalitabari, Sherpur.

Md. Abu Zafar

Department of Aquaculture,
Hajee Mohammad Danesh
Science and Technology
University, Dinajpur, Bangladesh.

Md. Monirul Islam

Department of Aquaculture,
Faculty of Fisheries, Bangladesh
Agricultural University,
Mymensingh-2202, Bangladesh.

Md. Abdus Samad

Department of Fisheries and
Marine Bioscience, Faculty of
Biological Science and Technology,
Jessore University
of Science and Technology,
Jessore-7408, Bangladesh.

Correspondence

Abdulla-Al-Asif

Department of Aquaculture,
Faculty of Fisheries, Bangladesh
Agricultural University,
Mymensingh-2202, Bangladesh.

Socio-economic Condition of Fish Farmer and Trader at the Village of Pitambarpur in Chaugachha Upazilla in Jessore, Bangladesh

**BM Newaz Sharif, Abdulla-Al-Asif, Suvashis Vaumik, Md. Abu Zafar,
Md. Monirul Islam, Md. Abdus Samad**

Abstract

The study was conducted at pitambarpur, under the union of shinghajhully, Chaugachha, Jessore in Bangladesh. The study period was carried out during September to December, 2014. In the selected areas, the study was conducted on 45 persons. The collected information was totally interview and observation based study. In the study area it was found that 54% farmers used semi pucca, 19% of fish farmers used to live pucca houses and rest of 27% farmers used to live earthen houses. The percentage of age distribution was 5% farmer was 25-35 years, 10% farmer was 35-40 years and rest 85% farmer has the age of 40 and above. It was observed that 5% of finance are contributed by farmers, 73% farmers got finance from bank whereas 22% farmers took finance from local moneylenders. About 97% of the fish farmers used tube well and rest 3% of the farmer uses pond water. In Pitambarpur 90% of farmers are illiterate and rest 10% farmers are literate. About 45% traders has own bank account but only 55% traders has no bank account. They exchange their money by cash or liquid money. It was found that 5% of concrete toilet and 50% has earthen toilet and 45% has semi-pucca toilet. After toilet work 100% farmer and farmer's family member use soap or basic substance. In case of illness 95% of traders and farmer's family served by quack doctor treatment, only 5% farmer goes to MBBS doctor. Almost 98% farmer's children are used to go school. Rest of 2% children is used to go with his father's work. About 97% of total income comes from fish business and 3% involve in others occupation. The rest 3% has secondary business like tea stall business, agricultural activity, and motorized vehicle operation etc. About 99% farmers use mobile phone and only 1% has no mobile phone. In Pitambarpur all of the farmers are Muslim. Most of the farmers and traders has 5 to 6 member in family, and usually they lived as a nuclear family. In the present study area 86% of farmer and trader have nuclear family. Rest of 14% has joint family.

Keywords: Socio-economic condition, fish farmer, trader, Jessore

Introduction

Aquaculture is a significant socio-economic activity, especially for rural communities, contributing to livelihoods, food security and poverty reduction through such mechanisms as income generation, employment, services, diversified farming practices, domestic and international trade and other economic investments serving the sector (Edwards, 2000) [6]. There is a long history behind Chaugachha. It is named after the four banyan tree beside the Chaugachha. Chaugachha is located at 23.2667°N 89.0250°E. The main city is on the bank of the river Kopothakho River. It has a total area of 269.31 km². The socio-economic characteristics pertaining to demography, means of production and investment, income and expenditure pattern of people living in a particular location strongly influence their responses to technological changes and participation in development schemes. The present study was an attempt to examine the socio-economic dimensions of fish farming and trading community of the village of Pitambarpur.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at pitambarpur, under the union of shinghajhully, Chaugachha, Jessore in Bangladesh. The study period was carried out during September to December, 2014. In the selected areas, the study was conducted on 45 persons. The collected information was totally interview and observation based study. The fish farmer and traders were selected on the basis of the random sampling method. For this study the necessary data were collected from primary data collection method. Data were analyzed by using MS Excel 2007. The study area is shown in figure no 1.

Fig 1: Map of Chaugachha Upazilla, Red marker showing study area.

Results

Accommodation Facilities

In the study area the fish farmers used to live in three types of houses such as earthen houses, Semi pucca and pucca houses. In the study area it was found that 54% farmers used semi pucca, 19% of fish farmers used to live pucca houses and rest of 27% farmers used to live earthen houses respectively. Housing condition of farmers is shown in figure 2.

Fig 2: Housing condition of farmers

Age Distribution of Farmer

In the study area most of the farmer has age of above 40 years. The percentage of age distribution was 5% farmer was 25-35

years, 10% farmer was 35-40 years and rest 85% farmer has the age of 40 and above. Age distribution of fish trades and farmers is shown in figure 3.

Fig 3: Age distribution of fish trades

Financial Facilities

Most of the farmers involved in fish trading are poor and their financial facilities are very low. In the study area, it was observed that 5% of credits are contributed by farmers, 73% farmers got finance from bank whereas 22% farmers took loan from local moneylenders with high interest of finance. Financial facilities of farmers are shown in figure 4.

Fig 4: Financial facilities of farmers

Drinking water facilities

In the study area the farmers were mainly depend on tube well water for drinking purposes. In present study, 97% of the fish farmers used tube well and rest 3% of the farmer uses pond water. Drinking water facilities of farmers is shown in figure 5.

Fig 5: Drinking water facilities

Educational Status

In the present study area most of the farmers involve in fish trading are not educated. In Pitambarpur 90% of farmers are illiterate and rest 10% farmers are literate. Educational status of fish farmers is shown in figure 6.

Fig 6: Educational status of fish farmer

Bank account holder

In the study area it was observed that 45% traders has own bank account but only 55% traders has no bank account. They exchange their money by cash or liquid money. Sometimes they use mobile banking like bKash, Datch Bangla Bank Limited and other money transaction system. Percentage Bank account holder of fish farmers is shown in figure 7.

Fig 7: Percentage Bank account holder in study area.

Sanitation facilities

Among fish farmers and traders of Pitambarpur the sanitation facilities are present 100%. They use three types of toilets concrete toilet, earthen toilet and semi-pucca toilet. It was found that 5% of concrete toilet and 50% of fish farmer has earthen toilet and 45% farmer has semi-pucca toilet. After finishing toilet work 100% farmer and farmers family member use soap or basic substance. Sanitation facilities of fish farmer are shown in figure 8.

Fig 8: Sanitation facilities of fish farmer

Medical facilities

In the study area among traders in case of illness 95% of traders and farmer’s family served by quack doctor treatment, only 5% farmer goes to MBBS doctor. In case of major illness they used to go Chaugachha Upazilla government hospital. Medical facilities of fish farmer are shown in figure 9.

Fig 9: Medical facilities of fish farmer

Educational status of farmer’s children

In the study area, major portion of farmer’s children are used to go school and colleges. Almost 98% farmer’s children are

used to go school. Rest of 2% children is used to go with his father's work. Educational Status of Fish farmer's Children is shown in figure 10.

Fig 10: Educational Status of Fish farmer's Children

Income sources

Most of the fish farmers and traders depend on fish business and their income come from this business. In the study area 97% of total income of farmer and trader comes from fish business and 3% involve in others occupation. The rest 3% has secondary business like tea stall business, agricultural activity, and motorized vehicle operation etc. Income source of fish farmer is shown in figure 11.

Fig 11: Income sources of fish farmer

Phone user

In the study area most of the farmers use mobile phone. It was observed that 99% farmers use mobile phone and only 1% has no mobile phone. No farmer can't access to internet or can't operate internet. Phone use in farmer is shown in figure 12.

Fig 12: Phone use in farmer

Religious status

Both Hindus and Muslims are involved in fish culture. But in the study area all of the farmers are Muslim. Religious status of fish farmer is shown in figure 13.

Fig 13: Religious status of fish farmer

Family type

Most of the farmers and traders has 5to 6 member in family, and usually they lived as a nuclear family. In the present study area 86% of farmer and trader have nuclear family. Rest of 14% has joint family. Family type percentage of fish farmer is shown in figure 14.

Fig 14: Family type percentage of fish farmer

Discussion

In the study area the fish farmers used to live in three types of houses such as earthen houses, Semi pucca and pucca houses. In the study area it was found that 54% farmers used semi pucca, 19% of fish farmers used to live pucca houses and rest of 27% farmers used to live earthen houses respectively. Molla, M. A. G. *et al.*, (2009) [10] reported that the crab collectors lived in four types of houses such as mud wall with golpata shed, mud wall with tin shed, semi pucca and pucca houses. Most of the crab collectors (62.50%) lived in tin shed houses, whereas 12.50%, 16.67% and 8.33%, crab collectors lived in mud walled with golpata shed, semi-pucca and pucca houses, respectively. Hossain, M. A. *et al.*, (2015) [7] Fish retailers in Dinajpur sadar were found to live in different types of houses which were grouped into Kacha (43.33%), Semi-pacca (26.67%), Pacca (30%). Which is more or less similar with my study.

Ali, M.H. *et al.*, was found that (2008) [1] Out of total 50 farmers, 52% belonged to the age group of 31 to 40 years whereas only 6% are found in the group of above 51 year. In our present study most of the farmer has age of above 40

years. The percentage of age distribution was 5% farmer was 25-35 years, 10% farmer was 35-40 years and rest 85% farmer has the age of 40 and above. The present study is relevant with the previous work.

In the study area, it was observed that 5% of credits are contributed by farmers, 73% farmers got loan from bank whereas 22% farmers took loan from local moneylenders. Sharif and Asif (2015) [12] reported that about 25% of credit are contributed by nurserer, 40% farmers got loan from bank whereas 35% farmers took loan from local moneylenders with high interest of credit. Quddus *et al.*, (2000) [11] found that, only 34% farmers got bank loan for fish culture while majority (53%) of farmers expend from their own sources. Asif *et al.*, (2014) reported that the nursery operators need credit support at the beginning of the season for pond preparation and collection of necessary inputs in Jessore region. It was observed that 24% farmers got loan from bank whereas 31% farmers took loan from local moneylenders with high interest of credit. The present study is more or less with the previous work.

Kabir *et al.*, (2012) [8] also found that 100% traders' household used tube-well water for drinking purposes, among them 40% had their own tube-well, 50% used shared tube-well and remaining 10% used neighbors tube-well. In the present study area the farmers were mainly depend on tube well water for drinking purposes. In present study, 97% of the fish farmers used tube well and rest 3% of the farmer uses pond water. The data is relevant with the present study.

In the present study area most of the farmers involve in fish trading are not educated. In Pitamborpur 90% of farmers are illiterate and rest 10% farmers are literate. Asif *et al.*, (2015) [12] reported that about 46% of traders have institutional education that range from primary to higher education and other 54% of traders have no experience in education in Chachra region. Khan, M.S. (1986) [9] stated that the level of education is a factor affecting utilization of pond for fish farming. The reported literacy rate was found higher than the national adult literacy level of 65% (BBS, 2002) [5]. Zaman *et al.*, (2006) [13] found that 23.3% fish farmers and traders were illiterate whereas 14.4%, 8.9% and 6.7% were educated up to primary, secondary and higher secondary or above level respectively. The previous work is relevant with our present study.

Asif *et al.*, (2015) [12] observed that 92% traders has own bank account but only 7% traders uses their bank account when they trade fry and fingerling. Other traders use cash or mobile banking like bKash, Mcash, DBBL mobile bank and eCash etc. In the study area it was observed that 45% traders has own bank account but only 55% traders has no bank account. They exchange their money by cash or liquid money. The previous work is relevant with our present study.

Among fish farmers and traders of Pitamborpur the sanitation facilities are present 100%. They use three types of toilets concrete toilet, earthen toilet and semi-pucca toilet. It was found that 5% of concrete toilet and 50% of fish farmer has earthen toilet and 45% farmer has semi-pucca toilet. Asif *et al.*, (2015) [4] found that 69% and 31% of fish farmers used semipucca and pucca toilet respectively. Where Ali *et al.*, (2009) [2] in his study found that 62.5% of the farmers had semi-pucca, 25% had kancha and 12.5% had pucca toilet. The data is relevant with the present study.

In the study area among traders in case of illness 95% of traders and farmer's family served by quack doctor treatment, only 5% farmer goes to MBBS doctor. Asif *et al.*, (2015) [12]

found that In case of illness 58% of traders and trader's family uses government hospital, least 24% uses private clinic, 15% traders are uses local village doctor and another 3% does not get any treatment. Ali *et al.*, (2008) [1] found that 46% of the farmers received health service from village doctors, 18% from upazila health complex, 14% from district hospital and 20% from MBBS doctors. The present study is more or less with the previous work.

In the study area, major portion of farmer's children are used to go school and colleges. Almost 98% farmer's children are used to go school. Rest of 2% children is used to go with his father's work. There is no data available about farmer's children education.

In the study area 97% of total income of farmer and trader comes from fish business and 3% involve in others occupation. The rest 3% has secondary business like tea stall business, agricultural activity, and motorized vehicle operation etc. Ali, M.H. *et al.*, (2008) [1] reported that almost all respondents (60%) reported agriculture is their primary occupation. However, as a primary occupation, 14% of respondents stated that fish farming is their primary occupation, while 18% and 8% are occupied in business and service, respectively. The present study is more or less with the previous work.

In the study area most of the farmers use mobile phone. It was observed that 99% farmers use mobile phone and only 1% has no mobile phone. There is no data available about farmer's mobile phone use in Bangladesh.

Both Hindus and Muslims are involved in fish culture. But in the study area all of the farmers are Muslim. Ali, M.H. *et al.*, (2008) [1] was found that maximum fish farmers were Muslim (94%) while small proportions (6%) were Hindus. Highest percentage of Muslims fish farmers were found in Kamarbari (96%) whereas the increased number of Hindus (8%) fish farmers were found in Hamirkutsha. The present study is more or less with the previous work.

Ali, M.H. *et al.*, (2008) [1] was found that about 28% farmers lived with joint families and 72% lived with nuclear families. In the present study area 86% of farmer and trader have nuclear family. Rest of 14% has joint family. The present study is more or less with the previous work.

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